

CURRENT ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL
BANKS IN ORDER TO INCREASE THEIR COMPETITIVENESS

Eshmuratova Nilufar Zhurabayevna

Graduate student of the Academy of banking and finance

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Abstract. *This article highlights the current issues of commercial banks' activity development in order to increase their competitiveness.*

Keywords: *commercial banks' activity, modern banking standards, transformation program.*

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ
БАНКОВ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИХ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещены актуальные вопросы развития деятельности коммерческих банков в целях повышения их конкурентоспособности.*

Ключевые слова: *деятельность коммерческих банков, современные банковские стандарты, программа трансформации.*

The necessary measures are being implemented in the country to reduce the state share in the banking sector by selling a state-owned stake in banks to strategic investors with appropriate experience and competencies. At the same time, state-owned banks are implementing a comprehensive transformation program, including introducing modern banking standards, developing corporate governance, introducing modern solutions in the field of information technology, optimizing customer service channels. Modern experts emphasize that competition in the banking sector is a much more complex process than in any other segment of the economy, since the stability of the national economy depends on it. The main indicators characterizing the level of competitiveness are: market share, profit, financial stability. At the same time, analyzing the position of a particular bank in a competitive market, of the listed indicators, the market share indicator is most often used. Kazimagomedov, a well-known scientist in the field of banking, points out the vastness of the sphere of banking competition. Kazimagomedov considers the necessary condition for the ability to compete with other banks to have, first of all, sufficient capital, otherwise he justifies the impossibility of expanding activities and providing high-quality services to customers. In addition, in his opinion, it is important to have a sufficient level of asset liquidity, professionalism and erudition of the staff, in the age of innovation and information technology, a significant role is played by the availability of timely and high-quality information

about customer needs, as well as the introduction of new banking products (services) and the image of a credit institution, which is an intangible part of assets the bank. Domestic experts Khamrokhuzhayeva and Davirova (2022) believe that in order to increase the competitiveness of the banking sector in Uzbekistan, it is important to solve problems with low liquidity, lack of qualified personnel, methods of control and coordination of work, technical backwardness and subordination of commercial banks. Continuing the thought of the previous authors, Mirtursunova notes the need for banks to focus on digital banking aimed at improving the quality of customer service, which makes it a strategic weapon for maintaining competitiveness. Ibodullayev and his co-authors named the imbalance of capital, a high share of state participation, insufficient resource base and high rates of mandatory reserves of the Central Bank as the main problems of the development of the banking sector in the country.

In order to increase the competitiveness of commercial banks, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at introducing technological innovations (mobile applications for online banking, digital wallets and real-time transfers); improving the quality of customer service (individual approach to customers, prompt response to requests and complaints, as well as providing personalized financial recommendations and services); improved credit conditions (competitive credit conditions such as low interest rates, flexible repayment schemes and access to loans for various categories of customers); investment in data security and protection (use of advanced data encryption technologies, enhanced security measures and employee training); flexible and effective risk management system (rigorous analysis of borrowers' creditworthiness asset portfolio diversification and effective risk monitoring); cooperation with technology startups and fintech companies; cost management and rationalization of business processes (automation of repetitive tasks, optimization of the organization structure and the use of new technologies to reduce costs). The introduction of innovative methods and tools is an important aspect of improving the competitiveness of commercial banks, which requires the implementation of the following measures:

1. Mobile application development: the creation of user-friendly and functional mobile applications will allow the bank's customers to access the bank's services at any time and from any place. This may include the possibility of transfers, payments, loan requests, account management, etc.

2. Introduction of blockchain technology: blockchain technology can improve the security and efficiency of financial transactions. It can be used to speed up the process of transfers, confirmation and signing of documents, as well as to create decentralized financial applications.

3. Using data mining: Data analysis can help banks better understand customer needs, research and predict market trends, and optimize their operations. This may include using machine learning algorithms to process and analyze large amounts of data.

4. Introduction of artificial intelligence (AI): AI technologies can be applied to automate processes, detect fraudulent activity, personalize customer service and improve the efficiency of the bank.

5. The development of digital banking: Digital banking services such as Internet banking, online lending and electronic document signing are becoming increasingly popular. Investments in the development of digital service channels will help the bank attract and retain customers.

6. Partnership with startups and fintech companies: Collaboration with innovative startups and fintech companies can help banks introduce new technologies and develop new products and services.

7. Staff training and development: Innovation requires qualified staff. Continuous training and staff development will help the bank maintain a competitive advantage and successfully implement new methods and tools.

8. Development of personalized services: the use of data and analytics technologies will allow banks to offer personalized services and products to customers. This may include offering customized investment strategies, loans, or insurance plans based on the client's unique needs and goals.

9. Cybersecurity: In the context of the increasing number of digital transactions and data, ensuring cybersecurity is becoming critically important. Banks should invest in modern data protection systems, threat monitoring and identification, and conduct regular training of employees on information security issues.

10. Ecosystem development: Banks can strengthen their competitiveness by creating their own ecosystem combining various financial and non-financial services. This can be a platform where customers can access various services provided by the bank or cooperating companies.

The introduction of innovative methods and tools requires strategic planning and decisive leadership. Banks that successfully use innovations can improve their competitiveness and stay ahead of their competitors in the financial services sector. The combination of these methods and tools will help commercial banks to increase competitiveness, attract and retain customers, and improve the efficiency of their operations. Increasing the competitiveness of commercial banks will ensure sustainable economic growth and transition to innovative development in Uzbekistan.

The formation of an effective state policy in the banking sector will ultimately improve the efficiency of the national economy as a whole.

REFERENCES

1. Yuldasheva, S. (2024). TIJORAT BANKLARINING FAOLIYATINI ULARNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MAQSADIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI. *Iqtisodiy Taraqqiyot Va Tahlil*, 2(1), 186–194. <https://doi.org/10.60078/2992-877X-2024-vol2-iss1-pp186-194>
2. Abdulazizovich, Abduvakhidov Akmal, and Kamilova Sanobar Mirdjamolovna. "ISSUES OF BANKING SYSTEM DIGITALIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN." *World Bulletin of Management and Law* 11 (2022): 14-19.
3. Abdulazizovich, Abduvoxidov Akmal, and Obilov Mirkomil Rashidovich. "RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT VA UNING MOLIYAVIY BOZORGA TA'SIRI." *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research* (2022): 71-75.

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